

Mental health wellbeing of HEI students during pandemic outbreak

May M. Tolosa ■ Crystal Joy S. Basal ■ Drexvid M. Danseco ■ Jenny Q. Diamsen ■ Liezel B. Nastor

Abstract

The study is conducted to determine Higher Education Institution (HEI) students' mental health well-being; its significant difference in terms of demographic data of HEI students at St. Dominic College of Asia in Bacoor, Cavite. Other objectives of the study are to determine the state of autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, personal relation with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance among HEI students during the pandemic. One hypothesis has been proposed: There is no significant difference in mental health wellbeing on HEI students during pandemic outbreaks according to demographic data. The study gathered data using an adopted questionnaire from psychologist Carol Ryff, the psychological well-being (PWB) scale. Convenience sampling methods were used to select the respondents that will use the most readily respondents. The questionnaire is distributed to 104 HEI students, and all questionnaires are duly filled out and returned by HEI students, representing a 100% response rate. The respondents' demographic data is evaluated using descriptive analysis, which includes frequency distribution and percentage, while Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used to test the hypothesis. The study reveals that personal relationship with others has the highest score among the six psychological well-being factors based on psychologist Carol Ryff. In line with this, a high score with personal relationships with others is interpreted that has a positive relationship with others; concerned with welfare, capable of deep empathy, affection, and intimacy; give and take to human relationships. Furthermore, the study reveals a significant relationship between mental health wellbeing and demographic data in terms of sex. On the other hand, study reveals that age, civil status, place of origin, academic status, and year level have no significant differences in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic.

Keywords: Mental health well-being; HEI students; COVID-19 pandemic.

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Introduction

Our world is currently battling with a dangerous enemy right now. It is an enemy that is not even considered a living thing, to begin with but is hurting people. An enemy that can spread and make people ill. An enemy that cannot even be seen by our naked eye but is killing people, COVID-19. Covid-19, formerly known as the new coronavirus (nCov), has been called the Wuhan virus since the virus came from the province of Wuhan, China. It is a new strain of virus from the coronaviruses (human type). The large family of viruses causes illness in both animals and humans in the origin of the coronavirus. According to the Center for Diseases Control and Prevention (CDC), coronaviruses are named because of their characteristic of crown-like spikes on their surface. Alpha, beta, gamma, and delta are the four main classifications of coronaviruses (CDC, 2020).

There are cases when coronaviruses infect an animal. It can develop and become advanced as a new human coronavirus that can cause diseases that affect human evolution. One current SARS example of coronaviruses is the COVID-19, and the others are SARS-CoV (2003), and MERS-CoV (2012).

COVID-19 was also called the Sars-CoV2 because of its striking similarity not just in their names (coming from the same family of the virus) and in their genomes. Although it's still unclear, the said virus came from a bat that infected a pangolin that was eaten by a human. Covid-19's mode of transmission is through contact: direct, indirect, and droplets. Its source of infection is from the mucous membrane. As the virus enters into one's respiratory tract, it will begin to manifest the most typical symptoms like pyrexia (fever), fatigue, and dry cough, but other causes can be asymptomatic as well.

This virus attacks those with a weak immune system, including but not limited to young, elderly, and immunocompromised people. That makes them more susceptible to developing complications such as severe pneumonia, septic shock, and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).

It has now become a pandemic that as of December 4, 2020, there are 63,965,092 confirmed cases of COVID-19, with 1,488,120 deaths reported to the World Health Organization. Locally, the total cases are 435,495 nationwide, 26,916 are active cases, 8,436 deaths, and 399,005 recoveries reported by DOH-RITM certified laboratory as of December 3, 2020. The pandemic has been disrupting the lives of many people, including the HEI. Students, mostly at risk of struggling and experiencing changes within their mental health wellbeing.

According to WHO, mental health is a state of wellbeing in which a person is aware of his or her own capabilities, is able to handle life's typical pressures, is able to work productively, and is able to contribute to the community (WHO, 2018). Videbeck explained that mental health is defined as a state of emotional, psychological, and social wellbeing illustrated by fulfilling interpersonal relationships, productive actions, and coping optimistic self-conception and stable emotions (Videbeck, 2014).

One of the most affected groups of people that COVID-19 is causing major havoc is among the higher education institution students. They are suddenly being thrown into a vast ocean with no concrete materials to hold onto. Colleges and universities face a considerable adjustment from transitioning to full-time online classes because of the strict implementations of social distancing and leads to a series of quarantine and state of emergency cases to prevent and lessen the spread of the COVID-19.

As of the last day of March, there were 14 million US students who were affected due to the closing of their school campuses. It is both hard for the students and schools to meet up in the middle. Online classes have become an option and pave its way to proceed with the studies, but the campuses are closed where vital resources and support are present and conducive (Davis, 2020).

The pandemic has disrupted and has already taken a toll on most higher education institution students; there are reported increasing cases of stress. This is adding a growing concern about the student's mental health. Studies show that college students' anxiety, depression, and stress rates have increased dramatically in the last three decades (Davis, 2020).

HEIs are mostly having a hard time managing their mental health wellbeing during the pandemic. Before the pandemic, many students are already experiencing anxiety and are often exposed to many stressors while studying. There are many factors to consider that affect them and study into the level of mental health being to know which part they should look after, assess, and address the most.

It is essential to address and adequately assess the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students to prevent the worsening of the problem brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic. Naturally, studying implies issues and stress to many students due to different requirements needed to submit and examinations to pass. Other students struggled to comply with their duties, internships, or trainings while taking care of their other requirements and lessons. In line with this, it is natural for students to affect their mental health because of different stressors related to studying, and, naturally, students cope with the stressors they are facing. Since we are facing a crisis brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic, many precautions and safety measures need to be done to minimize and spread the virus, and these safety measures and precautions become part of the new normal that are imposed by our government.

Classes of the students worldwide are temporarily disturbed, and it requires meeting a lot of changes and challenges experienced by the professors and mainly by the students. The abrupt transition of actual classes in the school facilities to online courses using different social media platforms for learning made confusion and anxiety to the students because of the new method imposed on the students to continue the semester. Some of students are overwhelmed because it is an all-new method to acquire learning and lessons. The mental health wellbeing of the students during the pandemic is well-affected; other students may feel that it became worse compared with their school routine. Distance learning or online classes are imposed on the students, but these have many implications for the lives of the students. However, they are practiced long ago, especially in other countries.

Our country is more into traditional learning methods, and the readiness to embrace and practice distance learning or online classes can overwhelm students that may lead to stress and anxiety. The school workload, new method of education, and the pandemic threats have a great impact on the mental health well-being of the students that can affect the performance and attitude towards learning or even with their daily lives.

Now that the COVID-19 pandemic is a significant threat to human lives, the government of different countries around the world is doing their absolute best to prevent more casualties and protect the lives of their people, which is the most concern today. Imposing the new normal to the people, which has a significant impact on people's lives because it brought drastic differences and changes to our daily lives. It results in many stress, worries, and anxiety on how to cope with their daily lives while battling the threat of the pandemic Covid-19, and students are one of the many that are affected and experiencing these struggles. It is evident that the learning of the students is very well-affected but has yet to know how much these changes and challenges that the students are facing. Some may think that the drastic changes are too overwhelming, or others may fear the unknown.

In every struggle or crisis that people encounter, changes and implications to our lives are inevitable. Mental health is the first that becomes affected. It brings stress, anxiety, or even fears to human lives. Some cope quickly while others are having a hard time, and some counter these changes with their strength or with the help of their support system. Now that society is more open about mental health, many people are more sensitive and concerned about this issue. It is essential to properly assess the mental health status of the people while undergoing or when facing a crisis in their lives. As the pandemic brought changes to our lives and complications, let us also be sensitive and concerned and take care of our mental health like how we are concerned in strengthening and taking care of our physical health.

According to the previous study of Adams et al. (2016), college students are always prone to stress due to some reasons such as academic pressure or increase in academic load, by being away from their family and for those who are working and studying at the same time. Entering college, and as the academic load increases, one may begin to manifest mental health symptoms, one may experience substance abuse problems, and one may augment the symptoms of their pre-existing condition. Most cases for having issues with mental health begin at the age of 17 or during their young adult years. Conditions with a higher rate of cases are anxiety, depression, and eating disorders, making suicide the third highest adult cause of death. Adding the pandemic to the situation, which leads to more isolation and loneliness, exacerbates HEI. The transition from a regular classroom class to an online course disrupts their normal life making students more vulnerable to feeling trapped, inept, lonely, and weak. An online class in a country which has one of the slowest internet connections, an education system that is not prepared for an online class, the environment and situation that is not conducive for learning and the social distancing that is tantamount to social isolation is wreaking havoc to the customary life of a Filipino student. Furthermore, the strict implementation of "only one person per household can go outside" increases their risk of experiencing general abuse.

Anxiety, disturb sleep, and difficulty concentrating on their academic work, hence manifests. Most students are living in a virtual world right now, with unknown ideas of how they would be able to survive this pandemic, as factors mentioned above keep on piling up and affecting the state of their mental health wellbeing. Addressing this problem will help students and people assess and determine the impact of the pandemic on the mental health wellbeing of HEI students.

Additionally, to gain a deeper understanding of the mental health well-being of the students during pandemics, quantitative research is conducted. This research aims to know to what extent HEI students rates their mental health well-being during the pandemic regarding these six aspects of autonomy, environmental mastery, personal growth, positive relations with others, purpose in life, and self-acceptance. It identified significant factors through a Google web survey to measure mental health wellbeing and the demographic data of HEI students during a pandemic outbreak.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to determine the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students and its significant difference when according to their demographic data during the pandemic outbreak. The study used quantitative approach with descriptive correlational research design and mainly used convenience sampling for the HEI students of St. Dominic College of Asia.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the mental health wellbeing among HEI students by measuring the six components of mental health wellbeing specifically:

1. What are the demographic profile of the respondents?
 - 1.1 Students
 - 1.1.1 Age;
 - 1.1.2 Gender;
 - 1.1.3 Civil status;
 - 1.1.4 Place of residence;
 - 1.1.5 College year level;
 - 1.1.6 Academic status;
2. To what extent do HEI students rate their mental health wellbeing during the pandemic in terms of? What is the mental health wellbeing during a pandemic?
 - 2.1 Autonomy
 - 2.2 Self-acceptance
 - 2.3 Personal growth
 - 2.4 Purpose in life
 - 2.5 Positive relationships with others
 - 2.6 Environmental mastery
3. Is there a significant difference in the mental health wellbeing among HEI students during the pandemic outbreak when grouped according to demographic profile?

Methodology

The researchers have chosen the descriptive-correlational type of research to find out the relationship between the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students and the current pandemic outbreak. The study was conducted at St. Dominic College of Asia. The researchers chose this institution to assess the state of mental health wellbeing of the higher education institutions and ensure that there is a conducive, learning environment of the studies.

The respondents of this study are students in St. Dominic College of Asia, with the following criteria: ages from 17 to 40 years old and are officially enrolled during the COVID-19 pandemic outbreak last second semester of AY 2019-2020 and first semester of AY 2020-2021. The researcher utilized a convenience sampling design that would use the most readily respondents.

In this study, the researchers used a questionnaire survey tool that was developed by psychologist Dr. Carol D. Ryff, the Psychological Well-being (PWB) scale. The first part of the questionnaire involves the demographic data of respondents consists of four (4) item questions, which include age, gender, civil status, place of residence and academic status.

The second part pertains to the questions from the Psychological Wellbeing (PWB) Scale; scale has 42 questions and measures the six aspects of wellbeing: (a) autonomy (7 items), (b) environmental mastery (7 items), (c) personal growth (7 items), (d) positive relationships with others (7 items), (e) purpose in life (7 items), and (f) the last aspect is self-acceptance (7 items). The 7-point Likert scale is also utilized for the tool. The researchers used the Google survey form that was sent to the respondents' Google accounts. The researchers chose this kind of survey for the safety of the students and also because of the pandemic outbreak. Most of the questionnaires were sent through email and some through social media platforms.

The researchers have adopted and chosen the Psychological Wellbeing (PWB) Scale as a "questionnaire" and was used in conducting the research study. The researchers of this study showed and discussed the chosen questionnaire with their professor in nursing research, which he then accepted and approved. The researcher's questionnaire undergoes a series of validation to an expert in Psychology in Nursing, nursing education and nursing services and undergo pilot testing of 10% of total population.

Cronbach alpha in SPSS was used to test the reliability of the questionnaire used in the research. The Cronbach alpha scored 0.807, which means it has passed the required value of 0.70 for a tool to be considered as valid and reliable. The result means that the questionnaire for this study is fit to be used for collecting data.

The researchers noted some ethical and legal considerations that must be made by the respondents to be aware. The researchers are responsible for the protection of the participants, the institution and the data that the researchers collected. The adequate level of confidentiality of the research data should be ensured. The researcher's email account was password-protected and all gathered information about the participant was confidential.

Descriptive statistics such as weighted mean and frequency, percentage and distribution will apply. Moreover, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized to statistically answer the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, location, the frequency, percentage and distribution; to measure the mental health well-being inventory; and to determine the significant difference of mental health well-being during pandemic when graded according to demographic profile.

Results

Demographic Data of the HEI students

Table 1 shows that the majority of the respondents belong to the age group with ages between seventeen (17) to twenty-two (22) years. That is, seventy-six (76) respondents, who represent 73.1%. According to gender, majority of the respondents are females consisting of seventy-six (76) respondents and they represent 73.1% of the sample. According to civil status, most of the respondents are single, representing 92.6% of the population. According to the place of residence, most of the respondents are living in rural areas comprising of seventy-nine (79) or 76.0% of the respondents. According to the students' academic status, most of the respondents are regular students which represent 78.8% of the population. Meanwhile, the highest respondents in a year level are first year students with a frequency of thirty-three (33) respondents, representing 31.7% of the population.

Table 1. Demographic data of HEI students

	Demographic Profile	n	%
Age	17 to 22	76	73.1
	23 to 28	25	24.0
	29 to 34	1	1.0
	35 to 40	2	1.9
Gender	Male	28	26.9
	Female	76	73.1
Civil Status	Single	100	96.2
	Married	4	4.8
Place of Residence	Urban	25	24.0
	Rural	79	76.0
Academic Status	Regular	82	78.8
	Irregular	22	21.0
Year Level	First	33	31.7
	Second	25	24.0
	Third	19	18.3
	Fourth	27	26.0

Mental Health Wellbeing of the HEI Students according to Autonomy

Table 2 presents the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to the autonomy which is one of the factors of psychological wellbeing scale questionnaire of psychologist, Carol Ryff. The result of the study revealed that HEI student's mental health wellbeing according to autonomy is within positive results ($M = 5.07$, $SD = 1.47$) interpreted as "a little agree". Moreover, the results revealed that the HEI students had positive results in the seven (7) questions under autonomy. The statements are the following according to highest and lowest mean score; (1) "I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what other think is important" ($M=5.68$); (2) "My decisions are not usually influenced by what everyone else is doing with" ($M=5.43$); (3) "I have confidence in my opinions, even if they are constantly to the general consensus" ($M=5.39$); (4) "I am not afraid to voice my opinion, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people" ($M=5.33$); (5) "I tend to worry about what other people think of me" ($M=5.33$); (6) "I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions" ($M=5.20$) and (7) "It's difficult for me to voice my own opinions on controversial matters" ($M=3.14$).

Table 2. Mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to autonomy

Autonomy	Ranking	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
"I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important."	1.00	5.68	1.22	Somewhat Agree
"My decisions are not usually influenced by what everyone else is doing."	2.00	5.43	1.47	Somewhat Agree
"I have confidence in my opinions, even if they are constantly to the general consensus."	3.00	5.39	1.39	Somewhat Agree
"I am not afraid to voice my opinion, even when they are in opposition to the opinions of most people."	4.50	5.33	1.44	Somewhat Agree
"I tend to worry about what other people think of me."	4.50	5.33	1.65	Somewhat Agree
"I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions."	6.00	5.20	1.44	A Little Agree
"It's difficult for me to voice my own opinions on controversial matters."	7.00	3.14	1.69	A Little Disagree
Weighted Mean		5.07	1.47	A Little Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.84: Strongly Disagree, 1.86-2.70: Somewhat Disagree, 2.72-3.56: A Little Disagree, 3.58-4.42: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4.44-5.28: A Little Agree, 5.30-6.14: Somewhat Agree, 6.16-7.00: Strongly Agree

Mental Health Well-being of HEI Students according to Environmental Mastery

Table 3 presents the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to environmental mastery. The study results revealed that HEI student mental health wellbeing according to environmental mastery is within positive results (M= 5.61, SD = 1.80) interpreted as "somewhat agree." Moreover, the results revealed that the HEI students had positive results in the seven (7) questions under environmental mastery. The statements are the following according to highest and lowest mean score; (1) "In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live" (M=5.62); (2) "I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities" (M=5.50); (3) "I have been able to build a living environment and a lifestyle for myself that is much to my liking" (M=5.19); (4) "The demands of everyday life often get down" (M=5.14); (5) "I am quite good at managing the many responsibilities" (M=5.03); (6) "I do not fit very well with the people and the community around me" (M=4.03) and (7) "I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons" (M=3.13).

Table 3. Mental health wellbeing of HEI students according to environmental mastery

Environmental Mastery	Ranking	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
"In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live."	1.00	5.62	1.34	Somewhat Agree
"I often feel overwhelmed by my responsibilities."	2.00	5.50	1.24	Somewhat Agree
"I have been able to build a living environment and a lifestyle for myself that is much to my liking."	3.00	5.19	1.28	A Little Agree
"The demands of everyday life often get down."	4.00	5.14	1.69	A Little Agree
"I am quite good at managing the many responsibilities."	5.00	5.03	1.54	A Little Agree
"I do not fit very well with the people and the community around me."	6.00	4.03	1.88	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons."	7.00	3.13	1.83	A Little Disagree
Weighted Mean		5.61	1.80	Somewhat Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.84: Strongly Disagree, 1.86-2.70: Somewhat Disagree, 2.72-3.56: A Little Disagree, 3.58-4.42: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4.44-5.28: A Little Agree, 5.30-6.14: Somewhat Agree, 6.16-7.00: Strongly Agree

Mental Health Wellbeing of HEI Students according to Personal Growth

Table 4 presents the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to personal growth. The study results revealed that HEI student mental health wellbeing according to personal growth is within positive results (M= 5.02, SD = 2.04) interpreted as "a little agree." Moreover, the results revealed that the HEI students had positive results in the seven (7) questions under personal growth.

The statements are the following according to the highest and lowest mean score; (1) "I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time" (M=5.53); (2) "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth" (M=5.18); (3) "I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world" (M=5.04); (4) "I do not enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old familiar ways of doing things" (M=3.88); (5) "When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years" (M=3.87); (6) "I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago" (M=3.50) and (7) "I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons" (M=3.13).

Table 4. Mental health wellbeing of HEI students according to personal growth

Personal Growth	Ranking	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
"I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time."	1.00	5.53	1.34	Somewhat Agree
"For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth."	2.00	5.18	1.56	A Little Agree
"I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how you think about yourself and the world."	3.00	5.04	1.66	A Little Agree
"I do not enjoy being in new situations that require me to change my old familiar ways of doing things."	4.00	3.88	1.87	A Little Disagree
"When I think about it, I haven't really improved much as a person over the years."	5.00	3.87	2.02	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago."	6.00	3.50	1.94	A Little Disagree
"I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons."	7.00	3.13	1.83	A Little Disagree
Weighted Mean		5.02	2.04	A Little Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.84: Strongly Disagree, 1.86-2.70: Somewhat Disagree, 2.72-3.56: A Little Disagree, 3.58-4.42: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4.44-5.28: A Little Agree, 5.30-6.14: Somewhat Agree, 6.16-7.00: Strongly Agree

Mental Health Wellbeing of HEI Students according to Positive Relationships with Others

Table 5 presents the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to the positive relationships with others. The study results revealed that HEI student mental health wellbeing according to personal relationships with others is within positive results (M= 5.79, SD = 1.96) interpreted as "somewhat agree." Also, the results revealed that the HEI students have positive results in the seven (7) questions under personal relationships with others.

The statements are the following according to highest and lowest mean score: (1) "I know that I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me" (M = 6.13, SD = 1.14), (2) "I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members and friends" (M = 5.79, SD = 1.35), (3) "People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others" (M = 5.70, SD = 1.81), (4) "Most people see me as loving and affectionate" (M = 5.34, SD = 1.33), (5) "Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me" (M = 4.24, SD = 1.97), (6) "I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns" (M = 4.00, SD = 2.23), and (7) "I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationship with others" (M = 3.51, SD = 1.95).

Table 5. Mental health wellbeing of HEI students according to positive relations with others

Personal Relation with Others	Ranking	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
"I know that I can trust my friends, and they know they can trust me."	1.00	6.13	1.14	Somewhat Agree
"I enjoy personal and mutual conversations with family members and friends."	2.00	5.79	1.35	Somewhat Agree
"People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others."	3.00	5.70	1.81	Somewhat Agree
"Most people see me as loving and affectionate."	4.00	5.34	1.33	Somewhat Agree
"Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me."	5.00	4.24	1.97	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I often feel lonely because I have few close friends with whom to share my concerns."	6.00	4.00	2.23	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationship with others."	7.00	3.51	1.95	A Little Disagree
Weighted Mean		5.79	1.96	Somewhat Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.84: Strongly Disagree, 1.86-2.70: Somewhat Disagree, 2.72-3.56: A Little Disagree, 3.58-4.42: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4.44-5.28: A Little Agree, 5.30-6.14: Somewhat Agree, 6.16-7.00: Strongly Agree

Mental Health Wellbeing of HEI Students according to Purpose in Life

Table 6 presents the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to the purpose in life. The study results revealed that HEI student mental health wellbeing according to purpose in life is within positive results (M= 4.99, SD = 2.16) interpreted as "a little agree." Moreover, the results revealed that the HEI students had positive results in the seven (7) questions under purpose in life.

The statements are the following according to the highest and lowest mean score; (1) "I have a sense of direction and purpose in life" (M=5.66); (2) "Some people wander aimlessly through life but I am not one of them" (M=4.87); (3) "I enjoy making plans for the future and working for the future and working to make them a reality" (M=4.36); (4) "I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life" (M=3.98); (5) "I live life one day at a time and don't really think about the future" (M=3.70); (6) "My daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to me" (M=3.70) and (7) "I don't have a good sense of what it is I'm trying to accomplish in life" (M=3.64).

Table 6. Mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to purpose in life

Purpose in Life	Ranking	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
"I have a sense of direction and purpose in life."	1.00	5.66	1.44	Somewhat Agree
"Some people wander aimlessly through life but I am not one of them."	2.00	4.87	1.63	A Little Agree
"I enjoy making plans for the future and working for the future and working to make them a reality."	3.00	4.36	2.00	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life."	4.00	3.98	2.01	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I live life one day at a time and don't really think about the future."	5.50	3.70	1.97	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"My daily activities often seem trivial and unimportant to me."	5.50	3.70	1.92	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"I don't have a good sense of what it is I'm trying to accomplish in life."	7.00	3.64	1.99	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Weighted Mean		4.99	2.16	A Little Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.84: Strongly Disagree, 1.86-2.70: Somewhat Disagree, 2.72-3.56: A Little Disagree, 3.58-4.42: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4.44-5.28: A Little Agree, 5.30-6.14: Somewhat Agree, 6.16-7.00: Strongly Agree

Mental Health Wellbeing of HEI Students according to Self-Acceptance

Table 7 presents the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students according to self-acceptance. The results revealed that HEI student mental health wellbeing according to self-acceptance is within positive results (M= 5.49, SD = 1.99) interpreted as "somewhat agree." Also, the results revealed that the HEI students have positive results in seven (7) questions under self-acceptance.

The statements are the following according to highest and lowest mean scores: (1) "In general, I feel confident and positive about myself" (M = 5.17, SD = 1.70), (2) "My attitude about myself is probably not as positive as most people feel about themselves" (M = 5.04, SD = 1.68), (3) "I like most parts of my personality" (M = 5.02, SD = 1.72), (4) "When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out" (M = 4.99, SD = 1.59), (5) "I feel like many of the people I know have gotten more out of life than I have" (M = 4.93, SD = 1.47), (6) "In many ways I feel disappointed about my achievements in life" (M = 4.06, SD = 2.00), and (7) "When I compare myself to friends acquaintances, it makes me feel good about who I am" (M = 3.73, SD = 1.79).

Table 7. Mental health wellbeing of HEI students according to self-acceptance

Self-Acceptance	Ranking	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
"In general, I feel confident and positive about myself"	1.00	5.17	1.7	A Little Agree
"My attitude about myself is probably not as positive as most people feel about themselves"	2.00	5.04	1.68	A Little Agree
"I like most parts of my personality"	3.00	5.02	1.72	A Little Agree
"When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out"	4.00	4.99	1.59	A Little Agree
"I feel like many of the people I know have gotten more out of life than I have"	5.00	4.93	1.47	A Little Agree
"In many ways I feel disappointed about my achievements in life"	6.00	4.06	2.00	Neither Agree nor Disagree
"When I compare myself to friends acquaintances, it makes me feel good about who I am"	7.00	3.73	1.79	Neither Agree nor Disagree
Weighted Mean		5.49	1.99	Somewhat Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.84: Strongly Disagree, 1.86-2.70: Somewhat Disagree, 2.72-3.56: A Little Disagree, 3.58-4.42: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4.44-5.28: A Little Agree, 5.30-6.14: Somewhat Agree, 6.16-7.00: Strongly Agree

Significant Difference of the Mental Health Wellbeing among HEI Students during the Pandemic Outbreak When Grouped According to Demographic Profile

Table 8 shows the mental health wellbeing of HEI students during the pandemic and the demographic and academic profile of the HEI students. The analysis revealed that there is no significant difference found (t/F = 1.28, 1.59; p > .05) in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic in terms of age. The analysis revealed a significant difference found (t/F = -3.26; 0.00; p < .05) in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic in terms of gender. The analysis revealed no significant difference found (t/F = 0.45; 0.99; p > .05) in the HEI students' mental health well-being during the pandemic in terms of civil status.

The analysis revealed no significant difference in the HEI students' mental health well-being during the pandemic in terms of place in residence (t/F = 1.40; 0.24; p > .05). The analysis revealed no significant difference found (t/F = 1.48; 0.21; p > .05) in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic in terms of academic status. The analysis revealed no significant difference found (t/F = 0.77; 0.77; p > .05) in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic in terms of year level.

Table 8. Significant difference of the mental health wellbeing among HEI students during the pandemic outbreak when grouped according to demographic profile

Profile Characteristics	t/F	Sig.	Verbal Interpretation	Decision
Age	1.28	1.59	Not Significant	Accept the null hypothesis
Gender	-3.26	0.00	Significant	Reject the null hypothesis
Civil Status	0.45	0.99	Not Significant	Accept the null hypothesis
Place of Residence	1.40	0.24	Not Significant	Accept the null hypothesis
Academic Status	1.48	0.21	Not Significant	Accept the null hypothesis
Year Level	0.77	0.77	Not Significant	Accept the null hypothesis

Note. t and F values. * p < .05 (two-tailed). ** p < .01 (two-tailed). *** p < .001 (two-tailed).

Discussion

Profile Characteristics of HEI students

Based on the findings, the majority of the respondents belong to the age group between seventeen (17) to twenty-two (22) years old, which comprised 72 (73.1%) out of 104 respondents. The researchers believed that the mental health wellbeing of ages between seventeen (17) to twenty-two (22) years old are the most affected age group during this pandemic outbreak. According to the study of Panchal et al., (2020) young adults have faced a variety of difficult pandemic-related problems, including loss of jobs and university closures, which could have added to their poor mental health state. In the time of the pandemic, a higher-than-average proportion of young adults (ages 18-24) experience anxiety and/or depressive symptoms (56%). According to the studies, young adults aged 18 to 25 had the highest incidence of severe mental illness among those who sought mental health treatment. The mental health crisis that students in higher education institutions are experiencing mental distress related to institutional funding issues, as the crisis is causing an increased demand for financial and human capital to resolve this serious issue. Students are experiencing social isolation and a lack of social support as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result of mandatory physical distancing measures and social gathering limits, many students have felt distant from their home campuses, where facilities and services are normally available.

Mental health problems among adolescents and young adults are on the rise, and social media may play a role. According to a recent study released by the American Psychological Association, rates of mood disorders and suicide-related outcomes in these age groups have risen dramatically over the last decade, affecting students at higher education institutions in particular. Between 2008 and 2017, the number of people who encountered severe psychological distress in the previous month grew across the board, with the younger adults (18-25) experiencing the greatest increases (71 percent) (Twenge, 2019).

When grouped according to gender, majority of the respondents are females. The researchers believe that female respondents' mental health well-being is more affected by this pandemic outbreak than men. One study made by Kecojevic et al. (2020), it revealed that according to demographic profile, non-freshmen were said to be more prone to manifesting a high level of anxiety than freshmen according to demographic profile.

Moreover, it revealed that female students experienced significantly higher stress levels than males (Kecojevic et al., 2020). According to Hellemans et al. (2020), their study revealed that male and female students deal with the pandemic in different ways. Female students used social media in coping up (to reduce feelings of depression and/or anxiety) than male students. The researchers have thought that most female HEI students experience the negative impact of pandemics on their mental health well-being.

According to the civil status, most of the respondents are single. In one study, single people experience better mental health wellbeing than unhappily married people (Pieh et al., 2020). Therefore, the researchers believed that single people experience less stress as they have lesser responsibilities and can fully grasp over their mental health wellbeing and self-care.

Autonomy

The study reveals the findings of autonomy. The weighted mean is 5.07 which is interpreted as a little agree. There are a total of seven (7) questions which measure the "self-governing" self-directing freedom and moral independence of HEI students. The highest score is the statement "*I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important*" (5.68) which is interpreted as somewhat agree. The lowest score statement is "*It's difficult for me to voice my own opinions on controversial matters*" (3.14) which is interpreted as a little disagree. It means being concerned about other people's expectations and judgments; relying on other people's judgments to make important decisions; and conforming to social pressures to think and behave in certain ways. Autonomy is described as the ability to regulate one's own behavior through an internal locus of control (Ryff, 1989b; Ryff & Keyes, 1995). A fully functioning individual has a high degree of internal assessment, evaluating oneself based on personal expectations and accomplishments rather than depending on others' standards. They are less affected by other people's ideas and do not seek endorsement from 61 other individuals (Ryff, 1989b). They are based on their own views and are less influenced by other people's ideas. A high degree of autonomy indicates freedom, while a low level indicates self-consciousness.

Environmental Mastery

The study reveals the findings of environmental mastery; the weighted mean is 5.61 which is interpreted as somewhat agree. There are seven question in which three are interpreted as a little agree, two as somewhat agree, one as a little disagree, and one as neither agree nor disagree. Among the statements that fall under environmental mastery, the statement "*In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live*" got the highest score (5.62) which is interpreted as somewhat agree. The statement with the lowest score (3.13) is "*I am not interested in activities that will expand my horizons*" which is interpreted as a little disagree. This facet of psychological well-being is explained as the ability of an individual to choose and control the surrounding, complex environmental and life situations by means of physical and/or mental actions (Ryff, 1989b; Ryff & Keyes, 1995). Ryff (1989b) stated that attaining high degree of environmental mastery mirrors one's control over a given setting while low degree reflects one's inability to control the given situation or environment successfully. A mature individual can usually communicate and relate to a wide range of people in a variety of circumstances, as well as adapt to different contexts on demand. Controlling physiological and cognitive arousal can help athletes gain a better understanding of their environment and enhance their relationships with others. Imagery leads to increased self-awareness as well as a better perception of the situation and environment (Potgieter, 2013; Weinberg & Gould, 2018).

Positive relationships with others

The study reveals the positive relationships with others. The weighted mean is 5.79, which is interpreted as somewhat agreed. There are a total of seven (7) questions that measure the personal growth of HEI students, and four (4) out of seven (7) questions are interpreted as somewhat agree. The positive score is 6.13 with the question "*I know that I can trust my friends, and they know they know they can trust me*" which is interpreted as somewhat agree. The negative score is 3.51 with the question "*I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others.*" It means to give oneself a chance to build rapport and develop empathy towards the people around them and the depth of connection they had in ties with significant others. Good interpersonal relationships and belonging to a network of contact and encouragement are important components in the formation of trusting and long-lasting relationships (Ryff, 1989b; Ryff & Keyes, 1995). A mature, calm, and relaxed demeanor shows maturity and contributes to better relationships and consideration towards others. While good relationships lead to others' understanding, bad relationships can lead to resentment (Ryff, 1989b). One main characteristic of mental wellbeing is the ability to have successful human connections, with pathology frequently marked by deficiency of social functioning (American Psychiatric Association). On the contrary, social relationships are a source of both good and bad things, good and bad (Gable & Reis, 2001). In comparison to positive jolts, a long line of experimental and theoretical studies on "negativity effects" reveals that horrible is more grounded than fantastic in various spaces, negative boosts have more grounded impacts on a wider range of outcomes (Baumeister et al., 2001).

Personal Growth

The study reveals the findings of personal growth. The weighted mean is 5.02, which is interpreted as a little agree (positive result). Personal growth is described as a sense of constant progress or persistent effort to reach and recognize one's full potential. One sees oneself as evolving and exploring and has the willingness to try new things. Has a feeling of understanding one's maximum potential, sees development in self and own actions progressively, and adapting in a useful and self-reflecting manner (Harris, 2010). The highest mean score under the aspect of personal growth is 5.53, for the statement *"I have the sense that I have developed a lot as a person over time."*

In support with this result, a recent study revealed that few students had reported positive changes from the COVID-19 pandemic which includes optimism, growth, adaptation and empathy (Browning et al., 2021). According to a study conducted by Rogers, in order to become thorough functional individuals, individuals must first consider how the environment has influenced them, and then address any problems that are impeding their progress toward realizing their real potential (Rogers, 1961). Another study revealed that being optimistic and growth-oriented goals is linked to having a higher self-development. Individuals who work harder in balance and become high functioning people are known to premier lives of higher well-being (Sheldon & Kasser, 2001). A high functioning person is always ready and open to changes and is constantly improving as a person (Harris, 2010). Research revealed that striving for personal growth yields enhanced well-being (Sheldon & Kasser, 2001). On the contrary, according to Australian Psychological Society, students felt fatigue, sadness, physical tiredness, loss of interest in their previous hobbies, emotional frustration, anxiety, and fear during lockdown (Australian Psychological Society, 2020). Furthermore, sleep disturbances, uncertainty, loneliness, irritability, fear and lack of motivation manifests as well (Labrague & Ballad, 2021).

Based on different study results, there are still small numbers of students who feel positive about their personal growth, but other studies have emphasized that more students are feeling the negative impact of the pandemic on their mental health and wellbeing that also manifest on their physical health.

Purpose in Life

The study reveals the findings of purpose in life, the weighted mean is 4.99 which is interpreted as a little agree (positive result). People with positive purpose in life have goals in life and sense of directedness; feel there is meaning to present and past life; hold beliefs that give life purpose; have aims and objectives for living (Ryff, 2014). The highest mean score under the aspect of purpose in life is 5.66, for the statement *"I have a sense of direction and purpose in life."*

In a similar study shows that, during the pandemic, psychological qualities such as purpose in life, endurance, and hope were discovered to greatly improve mental health (Arslan et al., 2022). According to another study conducted by Frankl (1992), people's levels of purpose in life vary. Those that have a sense of meaning and reason in life will live even longer in tough times than those who do not. In the wide range of stressors that people can encounter in the face of adversities like the present pandemic, they can nevertheless work successfully by reverting to their own essence of seeking meaning of life.

In contrast, the study of Arslan et al. (2022) revealed that purpose in life has negative and important predictive impact on psychological health issues (such as depression, anxiety, and somatization), both of which are poor markers of overall mental health. Furthermore, when compared to those without depressive symptoms, those with depressive symptoms showed lower levels of life sense (Klefaras & Psarra, 2012).

Self-acceptance

The study reveals the findings of self-acceptance, the weighted mean is 5.49 which is interpreted as somewhat agree (positive result). The highest mean score under the aspect of purpose in life is 5.17, for the statement *"In general, I feel confident and positive about myself"*. Psychological well-being will suffer if you lack self-acceptance, and beneficial treatments may be less effective for you than for people who have a higher level of self-acceptance (Pillay, 2016). Individuals who can achieve milestones like self-acceptance, self-actualization, and self-congruence are more likely to feel psychological well-being and lead a fully functioning life. According to Rogers' (1961) hypothesis, mentally stable people experience life to the fullest; as a result, they are regarded as fully developed individuals. In contrast, a individual with a negative self-acceptance score has a pessimistic outlook toward themselves, is dissatisfied with past life experiences, and wishes for different personal characteristics that are not bothersome to them (Harris, 2010).

Significant Difference of the Mental Health Wellbeing among HEI Students during the Pandemic Outbreak when grouped according to Demographic Profile

The analysis revealed that there is no significant difference found in terms of demographic data according to age, civil status, place of residence, educational status, and year level. However, the analysis revealed that there is a significant difference found ($t/F = -3.26; 0.00; p < .05$) in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during pandemic in terms of gender. Therefore, the researchers concluded that gender is a factor that has an impact on the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students. According to World Health Organization (2000) gender influences the unequal influence and authority men and women have over the socioeconomic determinants of their mental wellbeing and lives, their social role, place and care in society and their vulnerability and exposure to particular mental health risks. In contrast, according to Kantariya's (2017) study revealed that gender has no significant difference or impact on psychological wellbeing. According to the author the society gender bias does exist but does not affect the wellbeing of an individual and another reason is that families accept the gender of their child wholeheartedly and raise them without any bias.

Conclusion

Based on the study conducted by the researchers, the degree or extent of the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic outbreak revealed positive results according to the six factors of psychological wellbeing scale (PWS) of Ms. Carol Ryff. The results are as followed personal relation with others ($M=5.79$), environmental mastery ($M=5.61$), self-acceptance ($M=5.49$), autonomy ($M=5.07$), personal growth ($M=5.02$) and purpose in life ($M=4.99$).

According to the interpretation of Carol Ryff, positive result for the six factors of psychological wellbeing are as follows; (1) personal relation with others identify person has warm, satisfying, trusting relationships with others; is concerned about the welfare of others; capable of strong empathy, affection, and intimacy; understands give and take of human relationships. (2) Environmental mastery identifies a person who has goals in life and a sense of directedness; feels there is meaning to present and past life; holds beliefs that give life purpose; has aims and objectives for living. (3) Self-acceptance identifies a person that possesses a positive attitude toward the self; acknowledges and accepts multiple aspects of self, including good and bad qualities; feels positive about past life. (4) Autonomy identifies a person as self-determining and independent; able to resist social pressures to think and act in certain ways; regulates behavior from within; evaluates self by personal standards. (5) Personal growth identifies person who has a feeling of continued development; sees self as growing and expanding; is open to new experiences; has sense of realizing his or her potential; sees improvement in self and behavior over time; is changing in ways that reflect more self-knowledge and effectiveness; and (6) purpose in life identify person has goals in life and a sense of directedness; feels there is meaning to present and past life; holds beliefs that give life purpose; has aims and objectives for living.

Therefore, the researchers of the study concluded that the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students is not affected by the current situation brought about by the pandemic outbreak. Furthermore, the study reveals that gender has a significant difference in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students. Gender is a vital factor in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during the pandemic, the researchers concluded that gender profile of the student has to do with the characteristic of a student to handle life changes, different stressors and endurance when facing problem. In line with this, researchers believed that in every psychological factor different gender can excel, for example the autonomy and environmental mastery factor, male practice well this area since they are known to more independent and make decisions on their own. Researchers believed that females could excel more in this aspect since they can express their feelings and emotions well to others.

Recommendations

The current study establishes a connection between mental health wellbeing and the HEI students which then showed solid evidence the importance of assessing one's mental health, especially the students while studying. Based on the research study result, there is a positive outcome in the mental health wellbeing of the HEI students during pandemic according to the six-factor model of psychological wellbeing of Carol Ryff.

The researchers recommend that the parents should continue to listen to their child's problems academically and non-academically to boost their self-confidence and to make them feel loved and cared for. The researcher recommended supporting friends and family environments to help enhance student's ability to cope with adverse situations by improving their self-esteem and offering stress relief and through helping them develop effective interpersonal skills.

To reduce mental health distress, the researcher recommends that the school conduct an in-depth mental health assessment so that they can determine what kind of prevention to provide to the students. Socially, workshops, consultations, and class forums can help students communicate with others and speak up in a community setting. It enables them to express their thoughts and ideas verbally.

Universities and colleges should promote the importance of mental health wellbeing and raise awareness about self-care among students, teachers and staff of the institution to gradually eliminate the mental health stigma. The results of the study can also be utilized by the student and counselors as a guide into assessing and identifying factors that could affect the mental health wellbeing of the students, moreover, to help students address issues that are related to their psychological needs.

To hasten and develop their mental well-being, the researcher advises students to remain confident and welcome criticism. In addition, the respondents should participate in physical activities that they enjoy, surround themselves with positive people, seek motivation, and be thoughtful to maintain a healthy and high mental well-being. The researcher also advises the respondents to keep doing what they are doing as long it does not harm them. In terms of concentration ease, the researchers suggest that respondents concentrate on strengthening their weak areas. In addition, the researchers suggest that the respondents practice mental concentration strategies such as mediating to clear their minds, becoming an involved learner, setting goals, and doing or completing tasks one at a time. The most significant factor influencing the respondents' mental health is family support. An individual with high self-esteem is more likely to be loved, trusted, and welcomed by their family and others, according to the report. They are also more likely to be at ease, optimistic, and capable of engaging with others and establishing successful relationships.

The future researchers could conduct a study comparing the mental health wellbeing of the students before and during the pandemic outbreak. Future researchers could also conduct a study about the correlation of the academic workload between the HEI students and their mental health wellbeing using a larger sample of the students. A larger sample could facilitate congruence within the participants. Future researchers should also explore the roles of autonomy, environmental mastery, positive relation to others, personal growth, purpose in life and self-acceptance of the HEI students.

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